

CERN openlab: A Flagship Model for Industry-Science Computing R&D

Input to the 2026 Update of the ESPP

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Abstract: CERN openlab is a unique public-private partnership initiative at CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research), dedicated to addressing the ICT-related challenges of hosting the world's most advanced particle accelerator. Through strategic collaborations with leading technology companies, CERN openlab co-develops, tests, and integrates advanced computing solutions, ensuring timely access and training for the scientific community. Structured in three-year cycles, CERN openlab's Phase VIII, which runs from 2024 to 2026 inclusive, emphasises heterogeneous computing infrastructures, advanced storage solutions, low-latency interconnect technologies, artificial intelligence (AI) applications. Additionally, it supports diverse services both inside and outside CERN, enabling unique use cases and innovative solutions. It also explores emerging technologies like digital twins and new materials for long-term digital storage. The initiative's impact extends beyond high-energy physics (HEP), benefiting healthcare and climate modelling. CERN openlab further supports workforce development through training programs, summer student initiatives, and technical workshops, ensuring scientists and engineers gain essential computational expertise. CERN openlab fosters academia-industry collaboration, helping to maintain the European particle physics community's global innovation leadership and serving as a model for future partnerships.

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Executive Summary

CERN openlab, established in 2001, is a leading public-private partnership that drives innovation in scientific computing. It unites CERN with global ICT companies and research institutions to tackle major computing challenges critical to projects such as the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC). CERN openlab offers a structured environment for collaborative innovation, from early prototyping to large-scale deployment, significantly advancing areas such as commodity computing, data centre infrastructure, high-performance networking, and databases.

Entering its eighth phase, CERN openlab maintains four core missions: strategic industry collaboration, technological innovation, hands-on researcher training, and talent development, notably through initiatives like its summer student programme. Key R&D efforts are focused on two crucial directions: developing sustainable computing infrastructures with energy-efficient platforms and exploring emerging technologies, including scientific digital twins, hybrid HPC systems, and advanced archival storage.

Anticipating the demanding computational needs of the HL-LHC, CERN openlab emphasises the necessity of adopting and leveraging heterogeneous hardware architectures. The Heterogeneous Architecture Testbed (HAT) enables rigorous assessment and benchmarking of diverse computing systems, including GPUs, CPUs, and specialised accelerators, supporting over one hundred researchers with cutting-edge computational resources.

In Phase VIII, CERN openlab prioritises sustainability and innovation, highlighting projects in AI, real-time data processing, hybrid cloud-native applications, and novel storage technologies. AI initiatives leverage advanced deep learning for particle detection, real-time event analysis, and anomaly detection, utilising collaborations and access to leading HPC resources. Real-time data processing efforts incorporate machine learning on FPGA platforms and novel memory technologies to enhance efficiency and accuracy. Hybrid and cloud-native strategies, particularly containerisation through Kubernetes, have streamlined essential services at CERN, improving interoperability, resilience, and scalability. Strategic partnerships are modernising CERN's IT infrastructure through automated database lifecycle management and cloud-native technologies. New storage technology collaborations explore cutting-edge solutions, such as all-flash storage and ceramic nanolayer storage, to enhance data performance, scalability, and archival longevity.

CERN openlab's extensive education and outreach programs, including its summer student initiative and technical workshops, foster talent development, knowledge exchange, and collaboration between academia and industry.

Through its commitment to collaborative innovation, sustainability, and education, CERN openlab continues to significantly impact scientific computing, benefiting both high-energy physics and broader scientific, industrial, and societal domains.

1 Introduction to CERN openlab

CERN openlab [1] is a unique public-private partnership that has driven innovation in scientific computing for over two decades. Founded in 2001, it brings together CERN and leading ICT companies and research organisations from across the globe, creating a vibrant forum where cutting-edge science meets industry and technology. Together, these partners tackle the most demanding challenges in modern computing, many of which are vital to the success of the upcoming High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) [2]. Collaboration is at the heart of CERN openlab's mission. By providing a structured framework for partnership, organisations can co-develop solutions that push the boundaries of technology. This ranges from early prototype testing to real-world implementation, where innovations can be trialed at an unparalleled scale. Over its history, CERN openlab has successfully guided the transition to mainstream commodity computing, bolstered robust data-centre infrastructures, and seeded advancements in areas such as high-performance networking and databases.

Now entering its eighth phase [3], CERN openlab remains focused on four key missions: fostering strategic industry collaborations, fueling technological innovation, giving researchers hands-on experience with emerging solutions, and nurturing future talent. A key element of the last pillar is the CERN openlab summer student programme, which immerses young researchers in impactful, multidisciplinary projects while exposing them to cutting-edge tools and methods.

Looking ahead, CERN openlab has identified two primary R&D directions to address exascale-level challenges: *sustainable infrastructures* and *emerging technologies*. Projects under the sustainable infrastructures category focus on energy efficiency and optimised computing platforms. At the same time, emerging technology projects explore cutting-edge solutions such as scientific digital twins, hybrid HPC systems, and advanced archival storage. CERN openlab's agile project cycles, typically spanning one to three years, ensure that partnerships can evolve smoothly, adapting to the latest trends and breakthroughs in computing. CERN openlab supports both the high-energy physics community and its broader network of stakeholders by continuing to serve as a facilitator of technological experimentation and collaboration. Its emphasis on sustainability, innovation, and skills development extends the benefits of scientific computing far beyond CERN, creating a lasting impact on industry, academia, and society.

2 HL-LHC challenges

In mid 2026, the LHC will enter long shutdown 3 (LS3), where the accelerator and its experiments will undergo extensive upgrades to prepare the next run at a luminosity of up to around 3.3 times the current value (seven to ten times the original design luminosity). At the same time, the experiments will be upgraded for improved (finer) granularity and will be protected against accrued radiation damage. The current data analysis ecosystem is under-equipped to handle the expected data size and complexity increase when the LHC

restarts in 2030. Based on technological evolution, offline processing will no longer meet new demands unless new hardware architectures and heterogeneous hardware infrastructures are adopted and embraced. This also requires the community to significantly invest in testing and integrating novel hardware architectures developed both by the researchers and industry.

3 Heterogeneous architectures

The hardware landscape is becoming increasingly heterogeneous, with varied, often highly specialised and high-performing architectures entering the market in recent years. To tackle this problem, CERN openlab has established a heterogeneous architecture testbed (HAT), which offers the CERN community a rich ecosystem for assessing and evaluating novel architectures, with both on-premise and remote deployments. The mandate of HAT includes the reception, installation, configuration and benchmarking of new hardware; the maintenance of said hardware and software; project and user support; access grant and system administration; and organisation and support for workshops and training courses.

This setup takes advantage of the HEPscore benchmark [4, 5] for performance comparison across architectures, and the results are reported to and analysed by industry and research partners. As of January 2025, the HAT hosts around 95 systems, including the latest GPU, CPU, memory, networking, and accelerator devices. The HAT also provides access to remote facilities hosting, for example, AI-specialised hardware, and, through Euro HPC JU [6], to a number of Supercomputer systems with development access. It is used by over a hundred researchers in the CERN IT and EP departments and the four LHC experiments.

4 Phase VIII projects

The high-level objectives for Phase VIII of CERN openlab are to pioneer sustainable and emerging computing and storage solutions, to harness heterogeneous computing and AI for research and a greener future, and to foster synergy and technology transfer between industry and sciences. The following section highlights ongoing projects in AI, fast data processing for the HL-LHC era, leverage of containerisation for service deployment, and new storage technologies.

4.1 Enabling AI at CERN

Researchers are leveraging state-of-the-art deep learning techniques to enhance particle identification, pattern recognition, and anomaly detection in complex datasets. By integrating these models into the data processing pipeline, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential to enable faster and more accurate event reconstruction, significantly reducing the latency between data acquisition and analysis. AI is being exploited and investigated all across CERN, from the accelerator system diagnostics, beam dynamics, and control to real-time data selection and filtering at the LHC experiments, data quality

monitoring, simulation, and the final analysis. To support many of these workloads, CERN openlab is involved in a number of projects working to implement and optimise HEP AI algorithms and workflows for high-performance computing [7, 8, 9].

Collaborations with openlab partners have been instrumental in deploying AI on heterogeneous computing platforms, such as GPUs, FPGAs, and emerging AI accelerators. In particular, CERN openlab's collaboration with The Simons Foundation [10] gives CERN openlab researchers access to state-of-the-art HPC systems well suited for AI workloads. In addition to this, the participation in EU-funded research projects [7, 8, 9] and ongoing development and benchmarking access to EuroHPC [6] sites allow CERN openlab to leverage the most advanced HPC systems in Europe.

The development and optimisation of the Machine-Learned Particle Flow (MLPF) algorithm [11, 12, 13] has, in part, been supported by openlab. It provides an excellent example of how the power of HPC can accelerate development iteration cycles and enable optimisation workflows, such as large-scale hyperparameter optimisation, that would otherwise be practically impossible. Efforts focus on optimising the training and inference stages of AI workflows so that models are accurate, computationally efficient, and scalable.

In the interTwin project [7], CERN openlab leads the task of developing a prototype of a Digital Twin Engine (DTE) for Science, to support the development and exploitation of scientific Digital Twins (DT). The interTwin DTE is an open-source integrated platform underpinned by open standards, APIs, and protocols. It facilitates the development and implementation of specific Digital Twins. The DTE supports the setup, configuration and exploitation of Digital Twins.

Looking ahead, the integration of AI at CERN is becoming ever more critical. Through the various innovative projects described in this paper, CERN openlab is committed to harnessing advanced AI technologies as a cornerstone for scientific discovery.

4.2 Real-time data processing

The LHC produces billions of collisions per second during operation. Without selection or filtering, the experiments would generate Pb/s of raw data. It is, therefore, infeasible to read out, process, or store all of the data. The CMS and ATLAS experiments have implemented a two-layer triggering system to select the most interesting collisions for readout and analysis. As the particles of interest are rare among the vast background, the triggers must operate highly efficiently and with a low false positive rate. The first layer of the triggering systems must make a selection decision within a few microseconds of the collisions occurring, meaning they must usually be implemented in hardware-based platforms such as FPGAs.

To cope with the increased luminosity at the HL-LHC, fast machine learning inference is being developed to run on the custom FPGA boards that run the first level trigger of CMS and ATLAS. One of the first implementations of convolutional neural networks in an FPGA

for ultra-low latency particle calibration and classification was accomplished in the context of an openlab project with Micron Technology Inc. [14, 15]. Results from both experiments demonstrate that ML on FPGAs can be used to improve the selection efficiency and purity while keeping processing latency within the fixed limitations. New projects with Oracle Corporation [16] focus on applying ML-based anomaly detection to the triggers of ATLAS and CMS, building on work already done to deploy autoencoder-based triggers in FPGAs at LHC Run 3 [17].

In addition, Micron is involved in a project for real-time data processing on Compute Express Link (CXL) architectures, an emerging open standard for high-bandwidth heterogeneous, disaggregated computing [18]. A memory lake architecture providing shared memory for heterogeneous computing units with a coherent view is being demonstrated within the CMS data acquisition system, utilising state-of-the-art CXL-enabled memory modules to create a memory lake, by which data can be addressed by a set of host clients over a CXL switch, and perform near memory compute tasks for data filtering and reconstruction.

4.3 Hybrid and cloud-native applications

The tech world is witnessing a significant shift towards container-based systems, and CERN is at the forefront of this transformation. This move is driven by the advantages containers offer, including improved efficiency, scalability, and portability.

Kubernetes, an open-source system, automates the deployment, scaling, and management of containerised applications. CERN has already shifted numerous critical services onto the Kubernetes deployment model, including the Electronic Document Handling (EDH) system, Single Sign-On (SSO), Worldwide LHC Computing Grid Identity and Access Management (WLCG IAM), GitLab, Rucio, Service for Web-based ANALysis (SWAN), and many more. This adoption brings several key benefits, including enhanced interoperability across hybrid and multi-cloud environments, improved repeatability of deployments, increased resilience, faster deployment speeds, and automated recovery mechanisms.

Building on this foundation, the Phase VIII CERN openlab collaboration with Oracle is now focusing on modernising key services like the Oracle Database and Oracle REST Data Services (ORDS) using the Oracle Kubernetes Operator and other Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF) tools. This project aims to automate database provisioning, configuration, and management, simplifying operations and enabling GitOps for ORDS. Beyond these core advantages, CERN and Oracle leverage Kubernetes to address crucial challenges like sustainability, cost modelling, and disaster recovery.

4.4 New materials and technologies for storage solutions

The future data challenges HL-LHC poses extend to data storage and long-term data

archival. New projects with PureStorage [19] and Cerabyte [20] are designed to evaluate alternative and emerging storage solutions for requirements at the HL-LHC and beyond, such as all-flash hardware as an alternative to spinning disk and ceramic-based storage as an alternative to magnetic tape. CERN openlab aims to harness the combined expertise of both partners in storage system design.

Through these collaborations, CERN will explore the integration of Pure Storage's latest flash storage technologies into its large-scale distributed storage system, EOS [21]. The partnership focuses on optimising performance, ensuring seamless scalability, and addressing future scientific challenges. By working closely with CERN openlab, Pure Storage will contribute its R&D expertise to co-design highly efficient solutions, enhance the value of deployed technologies, and refine product development to better serve the evolving needs of CERN and other research communities and industries.

The collaboration with Cerabyte will enable CERN to explore the potential of ceramic nanolayer technology as a novel archival storage medium. This partnership provides an opportunity to assess the possibilities and challenges of this emerging technology. By offering valuable feedback, CERN will help shape its development to ensure it meets the demands of scientific research and large-scale data preservation.

5 Education and outreach

As part of its education and training program, CERN openlab runs various initiatives that support the participation of young scientists and other research organisations. Each year, the CERN openlab technical workshop is held, giving the opportunity for around one hundred CERN researchers and industrial partners to come together to review R&D projects and discuss future plans. The event features technical talks from scientists and industry and a poster session highlighting the work done throughout the year on openlab sponsored projects.

The openlab Summer Student Programme, which takes place each year, provides around 30 undergraduate and master's level students with the opportunity to come to CERN for nine weeks and work on one of the R&D projects under an experts' supervision. Openlab also provides a lecture series covering a wide range of up-to-date computing topics and specialised technical training for members of the CERN community.

6 Future Outlook

Over the next 5–10 years, computing will become the backbone of breakthroughs in high-energy physics, driven by the unprecedented demands of the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) and the planned Future Circular Collider (FCC). The HL-LHC will require exascale computing and storage architectures as well as advanced hardware accelerators like GPUs for real-time track reconstruction and FPGAs for low-latency, high-throughput data filtering. With processors surpassing the hundreds of core counts and power

constraints tightening, hybrid architectures (CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs) and energy-efficient accelerators will define the feasibility of discoveries in this data-intensive era.

The CERN openlab framework has demonstrated its effectiveness in fostering collaboration between industry and high-energy HEP research. Its structured approach to co-developing, testing, and integrating cutting-edge computing solutions has positioned it as a blueprint for broader collaboration initiatives. By extending this model to additional scientific disciplines and industrial sectors, CERN openlab can be pivotal in accelerating technological innovation beyond HEP. Fields such as climate modelling, healthcare, and advanced manufacturing stand to benefit from similar public-private partnership mechanisms, leveraging industry expertise to address complex computational challenges while ensuring mutual benefits in technology development and knowledge exchange.

As we look to the future, the Heterogeneous Architecture Testbed (HAT) is uniquely positioned to become a central hub for pioneering research into using the next generation of computing architectures. As computing architectures become increasingly diverse, the HAT's role becomes more important. Currently hosting nearly a hundred diverse computing systems, including CPUs, GPUs, accelerators, and AI-specific hardware, the HAT provides an essential environment for evaluating novel architectures. Expanding its scope will allow for broader benchmarking, deeper optimisation of workloads, and increased exposure of researchers to state-of-the-art computing technologies. This expansion will improve the efficiency of computing infrastructures at CERN and serve as a reference point for industry, facilitating bidirectional knowledge transfer and the co-development of next-generation architectures.

To fully harness the potential of the computing solutions developed through CERN openlab, involving a more diverse range of stakeholders within the HEP community is essential. While CERN openlab already collaborates with researchers from CERN IT, EP departments, and the four LHC experiments, expanding participation to include smaller HEP experiments, national laboratories, and university-led initiatives will ensure a more comprehensive exploitation of new technologies. By integrating a wider array of user requirements and perspectives, CERN openlab can refine its solutions to be more universally applicable, fostering broader adoption across the global HEP ecosystem. Additionally, increased engagement will enable knowledge transfer and training opportunities for a larger pool of scientists and engineers, further amplifying the impact of CERN openlab's developments beyond its immediate collaborators. In parallel, engaging a wider group of European technology companies provides additional benefits

Meeting the future demands of the particle physics community requires embracing new hardware architectures and a heterogeneous hardware infrastructure. CERN openlab has proven to be an invaluable mechanism for involving industry and accessing cutting-edge architectures in developing, testing, and integrating these new technologies. It currently hosts a diverse and influential set of projects across many domains.

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